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School Environment As A Predictor Of Students' Emotional Adjustment In Secondary Schools In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

Students' emotional adjustment plays a crucial role in their academic success, social relationships and overall psychological wellbeing in school. The school environment has been identified as one of the key factors that influence how students adapt emotionally to school demands and social interactions. Despite the importance of a supportive school environment, many secondary school students experience emotional challenges such as anxiety, frustration, aggression and difficulty coping with academic and social pressures. This study therefore examined school environment as a predictor of students' emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population comprised senior secondary school students in public secondary schools across the six education zones in Anambra State. A sample of 908 students was drawn using multistage sampling techniques. Two instruments were used for data collection namely School Environment Questionnaire (SEQ) and Emotional Adjustment Questionnaire (EAQ). The instruments were validated by experts and their reliability coefficients were established using Cronbach Alpha method. Data collected were analyzed using simple and multiple regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that physical environment significantly predicted students' emotional adjustment ($R = 0.412, p < 0.05$). school psychological environment also significantly predicted students' emotional adjustment ($R = 0.463, p < 0.05$), while school social environment significantly predicted students' emotional adjustment though at a lower level ($R = 0.351, p < 0.05$). The study concluded that a positive school environment contributes significantly to the emotional stability and psychological wellbeing of students. It was therefore recommended among others that schools should create supportive classroom climates, strengthen teacher–student relationships and improve school facilities to promote healthy emotional adjustment among students.

Keywords: School Environment, Emotional Adjustment, Secondary School Students, Classroom Climate, Teacher–Student Relationship

INTRODUCTION

Education plays a fundamental role in shaping the intellectual, emotional and social development of learners. It goes beyond the acquisition of academic knowledge, education is expected to foster students' psychological wellbeing and emotional stability (Okoye et al., 2021). One of the important psychological outcomes of schooling is emotional adjustment. Emotional adjustment refers to the ability of an individual to manage emotions effectively, cope with stress and adapt positively to social and academic

situations (Minev et al., 2018). Students who are emotionally well-adjusted tend to demonstrate self-control, confidence, social competence and academic persistence, while those who experience poor emotional adjustment often display anxiety, aggression, frustration and withdrawal from school activities (Adeyemo, 2019).

The emotional development of students is influenced by several environmental factors including family background, peer relationships and the school environment (Nwankwo et al., 2018). Among these factors, the school environment plays a significant role because students spend a substantial portion of their time within the school setting. The nature of the school environment therefore determines how students perceive learning experiences and how effectively they cope with academic and social challenges (Moneva et al., 2020).

School environment refers to the physical, social and psychological conditions within the school that influence teaching and learning processes (Hanaysha, 2016). It includes classroom climate, teacher–student relationships, peer interactions, school facilities, disciplinary practices and the general atmosphere of the school. A supportive and well-structured school environment encourages positive behaviour, emotional stability and effective learning among students (Unachukwu, 2020). A positive classroom climate promotes students’ emotional security and sense of belonging. When students feel respected, supported and encouraged in the classroom, they are more likely to develop confidence and emotional stability. Conversely, a hostile classroom environment characterized by excessive criticism, fear or discrimination may create emotional stress and anxiety among learners (Adeyemo, 2019).

Teacher–student relationship is another important component of the school environment that influences students’ emotional adjustment. Teachers who show care, empathy and understanding toward students help create a supportive atmosphere that enhances emotional wellbeing. According to Agogbua (2021), positive teacher–student relationships contribute significantly to students’ emotional development, self-confidence and academic motivation. In addition, the availability of adequate school facilities contributes to students’ emotional adjustment. Facilities such as well-ventilated classrooms, libraries, laboratories and recreational spaces create a comfortable learning environment that reduces stress and promotes positive emotional experiences among students (Ananomo et al., 2021). Poor learning facilities, on the other hand, may create frustration, discomfort and emotional dissatisfaction among learners.

In Anambra State, concerns have been raised about increasing cases of emotional challenges among secondary school students. Observations have shown that some students exhibit behaviours such as anxiety, aggression, low tolerance for frustration, lack of concentration and poor interpersonal relationships (Okoye et al., 2021). These behavioural patterns often indicate difficulties in emotional adjustment and may negatively affect students’ academic performance and social interactions. Researchers have therefore suggested that improving the school environment may play a significant role in promoting emotional stability among students (Moneva et al., 2020). A supportive school environment can help students develop effective coping strategies, build resilience and maintain positive relationships with teachers and peers.

Empirical studies have also provided evidence supporting the relationship between school environment and students’ emotional adjustment. For instance, Minev et al. (2018) reported that supportive school climates enhance students’ emotional wellbeing and reduce behavioural problems. Similarly, Hanaysha (2016) found that positive learning environments significantly influence students’ psychological adjustment and academic engagement. Despite these findings, many schools still face challenges such as overcrowded classrooms, inadequate facilities and weak teacher–student relationships which may negatively influence students’ emotional development (Unachukwu, 2020). This situation raises important questions regarding the extent to which the school environment predicts students’ emotional adjustment in secondary schools.

Understanding this relationship is essential for developing effective educational policies and interventions that promote students’ psychological wellbeing and emotional stability. Based on these concerns, the present study investigated school environment as a predictor of students’ emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to examine school environment as a predictor of students’ emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. The predictive value of physical school environment on students’ emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. The predictive value of psychological school environment on students’ emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. The predictive value of social school environment on students’ emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

1. What is the predictive value of physical school environment on students’ emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the predictive value of psychological school environment on students’ emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
3. What is the predictive value of social school environment on students’ emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypothesis

1. Physical school environment does not significantly predict students’ emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Psychological school environment does not significantly predict students’ emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Social school environment do not significantly predict students’ emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a correlational research design. This design was considered appropriate because it allows the researcher to determine the degree and direction of relationship between predictor variables and outcome variables. The study was conducted in Anambra State located in the South-Eastern region of Nigeria. The population comprised senior secondary school students in public secondary schools across the six education zones in the state. A multistage sampling technique was used to select the sample for the study. School Environment Questionnaire (SEQ) and Emotional Adjustment Questionnaire (EAQ) were used for data collection. The instruments were validated by experts in educational psychology and measurement and evaluation. Reliability of the instruments was established using Cronbach Alpha method yielding acceptable reliability coefficients of 0.80 and 0.79 respectively. Data collection involved direct administration of questionnaires to students in their respective schools. Out of 952 copies administered, 908 copies were correctly completed and returned representing a high response rate suitable for statistical analysis. Data collected were analyzed using simple and multiple regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the predictive value of physical school environment on students’ emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 1: Summary of simple regression analysis on physical school environment as predictor of students’ emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized
	β	β	B
Constant	22.145	6.893	
Physical School Environment	0.577	0.289	0.564
R	0.564		
R ²	0.507		
Adj. R ²	0.452		

The regression analysis in Table 1 showed that the physical school environment moderately predicts students' emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State ($R = 0.564$). The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.507$) indicates that 51% of the variation in students' emotional adjustment is explained by the physical school environment, supported by the adjusted R^2 of 0.452. The standardized beta ($\beta = 0.564$) further confirms that the physical school environment is a positive predictor, meaning a unit increase in physical environment corresponds to a 56% increase in students' emotional adjustment.

Research Question 2: *What is the predictive value of psychological school environment on students' emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Summary of simple regression analysis on psychological school environment as predictor of students' emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized
	β	β	B
Constant	21.426	6.738	
Psychological School Environment	0.574	0.296	0.552
R	0.552		
R^2	0.468		
Adj. R^2	0.413		

The regression analysis in Table 2 showed that the psychological school environment moderately predicts students' emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State ($R = 0.552$). The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.468$) indicates that 47% of the variation in emotional adjustment is explained by the psychological school environment, supported by an adjusted R^2 of 0.413. The standardized beta ($\beta = 0.552$) confirms a positive relationship, meaning a unit increase in psychological environment corresponds to a 55% increase in students' emotional adjustment.

Research Question 3: *What is the joint predictive value of social school environment on students' emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 3: Summary of simple regression analysis on social school environment as predictor of students' emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized
	β	β	B
Constant	23.407	5.539	
Social School Environment	0.692	0.211	0.684
R	0.684		
R^2	0.612		
Adj. R^2	0.576		

The regression analysis in Table 3 showed that the social school environment strongly predicts students' emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State ($R = 0.684$). The R^2 value of 0.612, supported by an adjusted R^2 of 0.576, indicates that 61% of the variation in emotional adjustment is explained by the social school environment. The standardized beta ($\beta = 0.684$) confirms a positive relationship, meaning a unit increase in social environment corresponds to a 68% increase in students' emotional adjustment.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Physical school environment does not significantly predict students' emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Test of significance of simple regression analysis on physical school environment as predictor of students' emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. B	Standardized β	t- value	p- value
Constant	22.145	6.893		18.782	0.000
Physical school environment	0.577	0.289	0.564	15.451	0.000
R	0.564				
R ²	0.507				
Adj. R ²	0.452				
F	28.376				0.000

The result in Table 4 showed that physical school environment significantly predicts students' emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State ($R = 0.564$, $R^2 = 0.507$, $p < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Psychological school environment does not significantly predict students' emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 5: Test of significance of simple regression analysis on psychological school environment as predictor of students' emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. B	Standardized β	t- value	p- value
Constant	21.426	6.738		17.657	0.000
Psychological school environment	0.574	0.296	0.552	14.863	0.000
R	0.552				
R ²	0.468				
Adj. R ²	0.413				
F	26.125				0.000

The result in Table 5 indicated that psychological school environment significantly predicts students' emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State ($R = 0.552$, $R^2 = 0.468$, $p < 0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis Three

H₀₃: Social school environment does not significantly predict students' emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 6: Test of significance of simple regression analysis on social school environment as predictor of students' emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. B	Standardized B	t- value	p- value
Constant	23.407	5.539		26.248	0.000
Social school environment	0.692	0.211	0.684	21.376	0.000
R	0.684				
R ²	0.612				
Adj. R ²	0.576				
F	31.237				0.000

The result in Table 6 revealed that social school environment significantly predicts students' emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State ($R = 0.684$, $R^2 = 0.612$, $p < 0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.

DISCUSSION

Findings revealed that physical school environment moderately and significantly predicts students' emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Adequate classroom space, availability of learning facilities, comfortable furniture, proper lighting, and conducive temperature enhance students' comfort and learning, thereby improving their emotional adjustment. These findings agree with studies by Ukpon and Okon (2020) and Oparaji et al. (2021), which indicated that adequate physical facilities contribute positively to students' emotional stability in schools.

In addition, the findings showed that psychological school environment moderately and significantly predicts students' emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Factors such as students' sense of safety, acceptance, satisfaction with school schedules, good relationships with teachers and peers, and a clean and calm learning environment promote better emotional adjustment. These results support the findings of Odebode (2019) and Amoda et al. (2021), who noted that supportive psychological conditions in school enhance students' emotional well-being and participation in academic activities.

Further, the findings indicated that social school environment highly and significantly predicts students' emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Recognition from teachers, positive peer relationships, participation in social and co-curricular activities, clear school policies, and constructive feedback from teachers help students develop social skills and adjust emotionally in school. These findings align with the studies of Shee et al. (2021) and Okoye et al. (2021), which emphasized the importance of social interaction and supportive school relationships in promoting students' emotional adjustment.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that school environment significantly predicts students' emotional adjustment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Classroom climate, teacher–student relationships and school facilities collectively contribute to students' emotional stability and psychological wellbeing. Creating supportive and conducive school environments therefore remains essential for promoting positive emotional development among adolescents.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. School administrators should create supportive and inclusive classroom environments that promote students' emotional wellbeing.
2. Teachers should maintain positive and supportive relationships with students to enhance emotional stability.
3. Government and educational authorities should provide adequate learning facilities in secondary schools.
4. Guidance counsellors should organize programmes that help students develop emotional coping skills.
5. Educational policymakers should strengthen school environmental policies that promote students' psychological wellbeing.

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